

Economic Importance of Tourism

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Abstract-

Tourism is vital for the success of many economies around the world. There are several benefits of tourism on host destinations. Tourism boosts the revenue of the economy, creates thousands of jobs, develops the infrastructures of a country and plants a sense of cultural exchange between foreigners and local people. These are not only a part of the tourism sector but may also include the agricultural sector, communication sector, health sector, and the educational sector. This is very profitable to local restaurants, shopping centers, stores, local people.

Introduction -

Tourism can be defined as travelling to a place which is different from your city or country for various leisure or business purposes and staying there for some considerable period of time at a length. It is travelling for some purpose and for stay which is not very long or permanent in nature.

Tourism becomes an activity which builds the base for the wide scale consumption bringing far reaching benefits. Tourism gains importance as an activity which has far reaching positive impacts on industries, economy, society and therefore for the whole growth, progress and development of a country. The definition of tourism also creates the foundation and the broad context of the tourism industry through which most of the advantages and benefits are received by the country as a whole. Let us now look at what tourism industry is and how it plays such an important role.

Objectives –

1. To study the Tourism.
2. To study about the Economic Development through Tourism.
3. To study about Tourism Industries.
4. to study the world Tourism.

Hypothesis -

1. All the people like the Tourism.
2. Tourism developed the Economy.

UNWTO Define Tourism Industries -

UNWTO defines 12 tourism industries that can be said to be serving the tourists in general. These industries are:

1. Accommodation for visitors
2. Food and beverage serving activities
3. Railway passenger transport
4. Road passenger transport
5. Water passenger transport
6. Air passenger transport
7. Transport equipment rental
8. Travel agencies and other reservation services activities
9. Cultural activities
10. Sports and recreational activities

11. Retail trade of country-specific tourism characteristic goods
12. Other country-specific tourism characteristic activities

Tourism Importance –

Tourism industry is important for the benefits it brings and due to its role as a commercial activity that creates demand and growth for many more industries. Tourism not only contributes towards more economic activities but also generates more employment, revenues and play a significant role in development.

This is the unique aspect of tourism as this creates demand for economies on global scale and more importantly for each country and even goes deeper in creating demand and growth opportunities at city level and local level for various communities. Tourism is also a commercial activity because the whole tourism process involves consumption of services and products.

The major economic, financial and even other reasons that make this industry important can be categorized under Economic value

1. The GDP contribution of tourism
2. The employment generation
3. The tourists it brings
4. The business it generates
5. The wide scale boost it gives to the industries of any country

Advantages of tourism -

The tourism importance for economies, for countries & their societies, and also at the global scale. Due to these 5 factors only tourism creates demand, fulfils that demand, increases consumption, and brings growth and development to countries and economies.

1. Tourism activity creates demand
2. Tourism industry value chain meets & spreads demand across industries & boosts more economic activities
3. Tourism requires country's wholesome development

4. Motivates to reach Global Standards
5. Tourism induces more consumption

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